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CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK MODEL FOR CLASSIFYING MAMMOGRAMS IN INTELLECTUAL DIAGNOSIS SYSTEMS

¹Fazilov Shavkat Khayrullaevich, ²Abdieva Khabiba Sobirovna,
³Yusupov Ozod Rabbimovich

¹ Professor, Research Institute for Development of Digital Technologies and
Artificial Intelligence

sh.fazilov@mail.ru

² PhD student, Department of Software Engineering, Samarkand State
University

orif.habiba1994@gmail.com.

³ PhD, Department of Software Engineering, Samarkand State University

ozodyusupov@gmail.com.

Abstract. In this work, we explore a way for analyzing a mammography exam holistically. We present the design and implementation of a deep learning model that takes as input the two mammography views (CC and MLO), as well as all detected breast masses and micro calcifications, and produces an output consisting of a three-class classification of the entire exam: negative (or normal), benign, or malignant findings. The registration of the CC and MLO views of a mammography exam is a difficult task due to the difficulty in estimating the non-rigid deformations that can align these two views, so we propose the deep learning model classification, with the hypothesis that the high-level nature of these features will reduce the need for a low-level matching of the input data.

Keywords: deep learning, breast cancer, CNN, mammogram, classification, intellectual system.

According to latest World Health Organization (WHO) statistics, breast cancer accounts for 23% of all cancer cases and 14% of all cancer deaths among women worldwide [3]. Breast screening mammography is currently the most effective method for reducing the morbidity and death associated with breast cancer in asymptomatic women [4]. A breast screening exam normally includes two mammography images of each breast: the media-lateral oblique view (MLO)

and the crania-caudal view(CC). For training and testing, we take the following dataset:

$$D = \{(x^{(p,b)}, c^{(p,b)}, m^{(p,b)}, y^{(p,b)})\}_{p \in \{1, \dots, P\}, b \in \{left, right\}} \quad (1)$$

here $x = \{x_{CC}, x_{MLO}\}$ represents the mammography views CC and MLO, where $x_{CC}, x_{MLO} = \Omega \rightarrow R$ and Ω denotes the image lattice, $c = \{c_{CC}, c_{MLO}\}$ represents the micro-calcifications (MC) segmentation in each view with $c_{CC}, c_{MLO}: \Omega \rightarrow \{0,1\}$, $m = \{m_{CC}, m_{MLO}\}$ denoting the mass segmentation in each view with $m_{CC}, m_{MLO}: \Omega \rightarrow \{0,1\}$, $y \in Y = \{0,1\}^C$ being the BI-RADS classification with C classes, $p \in \{1, \dots, P\}$ indexing the patients, and $b \in \{left, right\}$ indexing the patient's left and right breasts(each patient's breast is classified as a case because they can have different BI-RADS scores). There are six possible BI-RADS classes:1, negative; 2, benign finding(s); 3, probably benign;4, suspicious abnormality; 5, highly suggestive of malignancy; 6, and proven malignancy. However, the datasets available for this research only contain limited amounts of training data per class, so we propose the following three-class division of the original classes: negative, denoted by $y = [1,0,0]^T$, when BI-RADS =1; benign, represented by $y = [0,1,0]^T$, with BI-RADS $\in \{2,3\}$; and malignant, denoted by $y = [0,1,0]^T$, when BI-RADS $\in \{4,5,6\}$.

Convolutional neural network model. The deep learning model investigated in this work consists of the convolutional neural network (CNN), which is represented by $f: X \rightarrow Y$ (X denotes the image or binary segmentation map spaces while Y represents the space of classification vectors):

$$f(x, \theta) = f_{out} f_{fc} h_L g_L f_L \cdots h_1 g_1 f_1(x), \quad (2)$$

where \circ represents the composition operator, $\{f_i(\cdot)\}_{i=1}^L$ denotes the convolutional layers, θ represents the model parameters formed by the input weight matrices $W_l \in R^{k_l \times k_l \times n_l \times n_{l-1}}$ and bias vectors $b_l \in R^{n_l}$ for each layer $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$ with $k_l \times k_l$ representing the filter size of the n_l filters in layer l that has n_{l-1} input channels, $g_i(\cdot)$ is a non-linear activation layer, $h_i(\cdot)$ is a sub-sampling layer, f_{fc} denotes the set of fully-connected layers, $\{W_{f_{c,k}}\}_{k=1}^K$ (with $W_{f_{c,k}} \in R^{n_{f_{c,k-1}} \times n_{f_{c,k}}}$ representing the connections from fully connected layer $k-1$ to k) and biases $\{b_{f_{c,k}}\}_{k=1}^K$ (with $b \in R^{n_{f_{c,k}}}$) that are also part of the model parameters θ and f_{out} is a multi-nomial logistic regression layer that contains weight $W_{out} \in R^{n_{f_{c,K}} \times C}$ and bias $b_{out} \in R^C$, which also belong to θ . The convolutional layer is defined by

$$F_l = f_l(x_{l-1}) = W_l \star X_{l-1} \quad (3)$$

here the bias term b_l is excluded to simplify the equation and we are abusing the notation by representing the convolution of n_{l-1} channels of output $X_{l-1} =$

$[x_{l-1,1}, \dots, x_{l-1, n_{l-1}}]$ with the n_l filters of matrix W_l , with \star denoting the convolutional operator. The input X_{l-1} of (3) is obtained from the activation (logistic or rectified linear) and sub-sampling (the mean or max pooling functions) of the preceding layer by $X_{l-1} - h_{l-1}(g_{l-1}(f_{l-1}(X_{l-2})))$, where X_0 represents the input mammogram \mathbf{x} or segmentation maps c or m . The output from (3) is $F_l = [f_{l,1}, \dots, f_{l, n_l}]$, which is a volume containing n_l pre-activation matrices. The L convolutional layers are followed by a sequence of fully connected layers that vectorize the input volume X_L into $\mathbf{x}_L \in R^{|\mathbf{x}_L|}$ (where $|\mathbf{x}_L|$ denotes the length of the vector \mathbf{x}_L) and apply a couple of linear transforms:

$$f_{f_c} = f_{f_c}(X_L) = (W_{f_{c,2}}(W_{f_{c,1}} \mathbf{x}_L + b_{f_{c,1}}) + b_{f_{c,2}}), \quad (4)$$

where the output is a vector $f_{f_c} \in R^{n_{f_c,2}}$. Finally, these fully connected layers are followed by a classification layer defined by a softmax function over a linearly transformed input, as follows:

$$f_{out} = f_{out}(f_{f_c}) = \text{softmax}(W_{out} f_{f_c} + b_{out}), \quad (5)$$

where $\text{softmax}(z) = \frac{e^z}{\sum_j e^{z(j)}}$, and $f_{out} \in [0,1]^C$ represent the output from the inference process that takes \mathbf{x} as the input (recall that the input can be either a mammogram or a segmentation map of micro-calcification or a mass), with C denoting the number of output classes. Finally, estimating θ in (2) involves a training process that carried out with stochastic descent to minimize the cross-entropy loss over the training, as follows:

$$l(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \log f_{out,i} \quad (6)$$

where N denotes the number of cases available for training, which are indexed by i . The training of the model in (1) comprises a fine-tuning stage that relies on the dataset of mammography images and segmentation maps D . This fine-tuning will produce six models: (i) MLO image model $y = f(\mathbf{x}_{MLO}; \theta_{MLO,im})$, (ii) CC image model $y = f(\mathbf{x}_{CC}; \theta_{CC,im})$, (iii) MLO MC segmentation map model $\mathbf{y} = f(\mathbf{c}_{MLO}; \theta_{MLO,mc})$, (iv) CC MC segmentation map model $\mathbf{y} = f(\mathbf{c}_{CC}; \theta_{CC,mc})$, (v) MLO mass segmentation model $y = f(m_{MLO}; \theta_{MLO,ma})$, (vi) CC mass segmentation model $y = f(m_{CC}; \theta_{CC,ma})$

Finally, the multi-view model combines the six models produced from the fine-tuning process by concatenating the features from the last fully connected layer of all six models, represented by $[f_{f_c,i}]_{i \in \{MLO,im,CC,im,MLO,mc,CC,mc,MLO,ma,CC,ma\}}$, and training a single multinomial logistic regression layer using those inputs. This multi-view model is denoted by:

$$f_{out,mv} = \text{softmax}(W_{out,mv} [f_{f_c,i}]_{i \in \{MLO,im,CC,im,MLO,mc,CC,mc,MLO,ma,CC,ma\}} + b_{out,mv}), \quad (7)$$

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